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Working paper: A statistical exploration of the effects of phoneme class contacts in German noun-noun compounds

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This working paper describes a study that explores phoneme contact preferences in German noun-noun compounds with statistical methods on the basis of a large dataset (over 707,000 compounds). The following hypotheses are tested based on surprisal values: 1) vowel contacts are avoided → confirmed; 2) contacts of phonemes from the same phoneme class are avoided → not confirmed; 3) contacts where a phoneme with higher sonority is followed by a phoneme with lower sonority are avoided (syllable contact law) → largely confirmed.

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Supplemental material for this working paper is available via OSF: <https://osf.io/e7afd>

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1 Research questions

In this study, we examine the phoneme class contacts that occur in a large number of German noun-noun compounds comprising two simplex nouns and look for indications whether certain phonological contacts are preferred or avoided in compounding. We will focus on the following aspects:

1. Sonority: For syllable contacts within the same morphological word, phoneme contact where a more sonorous phoneme is followed by a less sonorous phoneme are preferred, while the opposite is avoided ('syllable contact law'; cf. e.g. Hall 2011, p. 230-236; Vennemann 1988, p. 40). Do we find evidence that this rule is also relevant for contacts between the constituents in compounding?
2. Vowel contacts (hiatus): Direct contact between vowels is sometimes avoided, e.g. in the context of derivation (e.g. *amerika-n-isch*, *ge-g-essen*). Can we observe such a trend in compounding?
3. Contact of phonemes from the same phoneme class: Contacts of identical phonemes tend to be avoided. As we don't have coding for individual phonemes in our data, we will address the more general case of contact between *phoneme classes* and check whether we can observe any tendencies that this is avoided.

2 Data set

Our data is extracted from the “KoGra Untersuchungskorpus”¹, which comprises roughly 7 billion tokens and is a subset of the German Reference Corpus (DeReKo, Release 2017-II²). This corpus consists mainly of German newspaper texts (over 90%), but also contains some literary texts, and about 6% spoken language material (cf. Bubenhofer/Konopka/Schneider 2014). Detailed morphological information was added with a custom word analyzer based on the Canoo Language Tools³. This made it possible to automatically extract a large collection of over 489 million nominal compound tokens that serves as the basis for our studies on word formation.

For this study, we used the same dataset as in Brunner/Engelberg/Hein 2021 (studies A, B and C). It consists only of compounds comprising of two simplex nouns, e.g. *Stadthalle* (‘town hall’). In addition to that, the constituents of the data set were annotated with categories from GermaNet (Hamp and Feldweg 1997; Henrich and Hinrichs 2010) and we kept only compounds for which a GermaNet match was found for each constituent. This had a cleanup effect, as it made it more likely that the compounds consisted of two plausible words. As there were still errors due to the automatic annotation, some additional manual cleanup was performed on the resulting list, removing compounds that contained constituents that were either not recognizable as words or were not simplex nouns. The resulting dataset comprises 707,910 compound types.⁴

The automatic tool gave us a segmentation of each compound, but only lemmatized forms for the constituents. For a phonological study however, we need surface forms, so we inferred the segmentation of the compound surface automatically, using the available information about the lemmatized forms. This process was successful for 704,475 compounds, 99.5 percent of the original data set.⁵ This is the data set this study is based on. A manual check of 200 randomly selected compounds revealed that 95% of the assigned surface segmentations were

1 *Korpus des Projekts Korpusgrammatik*. Leibniz-Institut für Deutsche Sprache: „Korpusgestützte Grammatik“. Grammatisches Informationssystem grammis. DOI: 10.14618/korpusgrammatik. URL: <https://grammis.ids-mannheim.de/korpusgrammatik/6615>.

2 *Deutsches Referenzkorpus / Archiv der Korpora geschriebener Gegenwartssprache 2017-II* (Release: 01.10.2017). Mannheim: Leibniz-Institut für Deutsche Sprache. www.ids-mannheim.de/DeReKo.

3 <http://www.canoonet.eu>. Unfortunately, this website no longer exists. Parts of the content of canoonet were integrated into LEOdict (https://dict.leo.org/pages/about/ende/canoonet_de.html; accessed 23.05.2025) but the morphological analyzer is no longer accessible.

4 For a more detailed explanation on how this dataset was curated, cf. Brunner/Engelberg/Hein 2021 p. 9-12.

5 Cases where surface forms could not be assigned were due to errors in the automatic lemmatization of the constituents, especially the head word.

correct. In the sample, all errors were due to problems in the original data, not the post-processing step: Either the input data contained faulty segmentations or the entries were not valid compounds at all.

Any linking elements were treated as part of the first constituent. So for example, *Staatsanwalt* will be segmented into *staats* (*Staat* plus linking element *s*) and *anwalt*. We have the information for which compounds a simple combination of the lemmatized forms of the constituents is identical to the surface form (e.g. *Afrikabild* – *Afrika* plus *Bild*). This subgroup contains no linking elements and was tested separately in our analyses (cf. section 3.2, end).

To study phoneme contact in compounding we needed information about the last phoneme of the modifier (including linking element) and the first phoneme of the head for each compound. We devised a rule-based system to derive the phoneme classes based on the orthographical surfaces, identifying eight phoneme classes that are ranked by sonority. Table 1 shows the labels used for the phoneme classes. They are comprised of a letter as shorthand for the name of the class and a number that indicates the level of sonority with 1 being the least sonorous and 8 the most sonorous phoneme class. Appendix 1 documents the exact rules that were applied to assign labels. Note that in this study, the approximant/semivowel [j] (first phoneme of e.g. *Jahr*) is classified as a high vowel and [ɐ] (the last phoneme of e.g. *Leber*) is considered a low vowel. The glottal stop [ʔ] is not considered a phoneme but a phonetic feature because in Standard German it appears predictably in certain contexts (word-initial or stressed syllables that begin with a vowel).

Table 1: Labels for the phoneme classes, ranked by sonority (examples are not exhaustive)

label	phoneme class	examples
1_p	plosive	[t] [g] [k] [b] [d] [p]
2_f	fricative	[s] [f] [ʃ] [h] [x]
3_n	nasal	[n] [m] [ŋ]
4_l	liquid (phoneme l)	[l] [ʎ]
5_l	liquid (phoneme r)	[ʁ] [R] [r]
6_v	high vowel	[ɪ] [ʊ] [i] [y] [i:] [u] [y] [j]
7_v	mid vowel	[ə] [ɛ] [ɔ] [œ] [e] [o]
8_v	low vowel	[a] [a:] [ɐ]

It must be noted that our data set contains a relatively high number of proper names as well as foreign language elements, especially English and French constituents. Though we tried to account for foreign languages in our rules to some extent, this led to some ambiguities. A

manual check of a sample of 200 compounds revealed that the assignment of the phoneme class was correct in 97% percent of the cases. The errors were all due to foreign language constituents. Table 2 shows an excerpt from the dataset.

Table 2: Excerpt from the data set (total size: 704,475 entries)

frequency	compound	modifier surface	head surface	phoneme class end of modifier	phoneme class beginning of head
2911504	Sonntag	sonn	tag	3_n	1_p
1758319	Donnerstag	donners	tag	2_f	1_p
1269620	Bürgermeister	bürger	meister	5_l	3_n
1160962	Wochenende	wochen	ende	3_n	7_v
781104	Geburtstag	geburts	tag	2_f	1_p
696116	Fußball	fuß	ball	2_f	1_p
467966	Landtag	land	tag	1_p	1_p
465068	Landkreis	land	kreis	1_p	1_p
449355	Kindergarten	kinder	garten	5_l	1_p
428906	Jahrzehnt	jahr	zehnt	5_l	1_p

3 Empirical exploration

There are two possibilities to use the quantitative data: Either we only look at the types in our data set or we also incorporate the frequency information we have for these types. Both approaches have merit: Considering only the types gives us an idea which distinct compounds occur in real life data. However, as each compound type has the same impact on the result, very infrequent compounds and errors in the data gain strong influence. If we weigh the types according to their frequencies, we get information about which distinct compounds are *common*, which is arguably more useful to tell us something about productivity and entrenchment in German compounding. However, as the frequency curve in our data set follows a Zipf-like distribution with few very frequent entries and a huge tail end of hapax legomena, the most frequent entries gain a strong influence on the results (c.f. figure 1). As both aspects are interesting, we will look at the distributions on both ways and discuss the results.

Figure 1: Frequency curve for the compounds in our data set (logarithmic scale)

3.1 Data distribution matrices

In the following matrices (figures 2-5), the phoneme classes of the last phoneme of the modifiers are plotted on the y-axis and the phoneme classes of the first phoneme of the head words on the x-axis. Each scale is ordered according to sonority (least to most sonorous). The cells show the values for contacts between those phoneme classes. For example, figure 1 shows that a contact between a fricative as last phoneme of the modifier and a plosive as first phoneme of the head (shorthand: [2_f + 1_p]) occurs in 47,751 compounds types. The cells forming the diagonal line from upper left to lower right represent the cases where phonemes of the same class come into contact. If the hypothesis holds true that contacts where the second element is less sonorous than the first are preferred, the cells below this diagonal line should have generally higher values than the cells above it. The 9 cells in the lower right quadrant of the matrix show the contacts between vowel phoneme classes. If the hypothesis that vowel contacts are avoided is true, those should have lower values.

Figure 2 shows a matrix of type counts for all combinations of phoneme class contacts. It is evident that some phoneme classes, e.g. plosives, are much more common than others. To get an impression whether there are distributional preferences besides simple frequency of the phoneme classes, we calculated the number of cases that would appear in each matrix cell, if the distribution were random – the expected distribution.⁶ For figure 3, we calculated which percentage of the expected values the real values represent. If a real number corresponded exactly to the expected number, the cell value would be 100. Looking at the contact [2_f + 1_p] again, we see that the value is 102.83. This means that it is 102.83% of the expected value, i.e. only slightly larger than expected.

Figure 3 indicates that the deviations from the expected numbers are not large, the cell values range between 73 and 111. The distribution of contacts between phoneme classes in compounds seems quite uniform on type level. There might be a slight trend that contacts with decreasing sonority are favored, which would support our hypothesis, but the picture is not clear.

We can, however, observe a trend that contacts between vowels are avoided, especially those where vowels of same phoneme class come into contact and those where the second vowel is more sonorous.

When looking at contacts between identical phoneme classes of any kind, we see that these are a little less frequent than expected as well.

⁶ There are statistical tests to determine whether the distribution in a matrix deviates from the expected distribution in a significant way; a common one is the Chi square test. If we run it for the matrices in figures 2 and 4, we do get significant results – so we know that the distribution is not random. However, when applied to a very large dataset such as ours, the statistical test can be misleading, as it picks up on small effects. In addition to that, the assumption of independence underlying the statistical tests does not hold for language data in general, which makes it even more problematic to rely on the test result. We therefore opted for a purely descriptive approach here.

Figure 2: Distribution of compound types according to their phoneme contacts (type-based)

Figure 3: Percentage of real frequencies in relation to expected frequencies (type-based)

We will now look at the token-based distribution, taking into account the frequency for each compound type (figure 4 and 5). The deviations from the expected distribution are much larger – while in figure 2 the values ranged only between 73 and 111, in figure 5 they range from ca. 38% (less than half the expected value) to nearly 300 (three times more than expected). We again observe a slight preference for contacts where the second phoneme is less sonorous and a dispreference for most vowel combinations, but there are outliers.

As mentioned above, the frequency curve for our data is Zipf-like with a very steep slope (cf. figure 1). If we take a closer look at a few cells that stand out in particular with much higher values than expected, we see that compounds from the highest frequency bands have indeed an impact: The combination [3_n + 7_v] (nasal + mid vowel) has the highest value with 294.55%. Compounds with this combination include *Wochenende* which is one of the most frequent compounds in our data. Similarly, the combination [3_l + 6_v] (liquid + high vowel), which stands out with a value of 274.44 %, includes the very frequent word *Schuljahr*.

Just removing the words *Wochenende* and *Schuljahr* already leads to a matrix where the respective cell values are much less extreme, but in order to have a more objective picture of the influence of very frequent compounds, we recalculated the matrix without the 100 most frequent entries (figure 6). The distribution becomes notably more even. The matrix now looks more similar to the type-based matrix (figure 3), albeit with stronger deviations from the expected distribution in both directions. Only the cell [6_v + 4_l] (high vowel + liquid) still has the value 234,72, i.e. more than twice the expected items. This cell contains frequent compounds as well (e.g. *EU-Land*, *Industrieland*), but is not dominated by a single entry.

Figure 4: Distribution of compound tokens according to their phoneme contacts

Figure 5: Percentage of the real numbers in relation to the expected numbers (tokens)

Figure 6: Percentage of the real numbers in relation to the expected numbers (tokens without the 100 most frequent compounds)

3.2 Surprisal-based measurements

As the purely visual exploration of the matrices did not lead to clear conclusions, we tried a different approach based on the idea of entropy. Entropy can be interpreted as the uncertainty when drawing a random element from a group. It originally stems from information theory (cf. Shannon 1948), but has been used for linguistic studies as well (e.g. Gibson et al. 2019; Tu 2024; Koplenig et al. 2024).

For our study, we use the measurement of information content which is a component when calculating entropy. The information content of an event E is defined as

$$I(E) = -\log_2(p(E))$$

where $p(E)$ is the probability of the event. In our context we are interested in the probability of a specific phoneme class occurring at the beginning of the head, given the phoneme class of the last phoneme of the modifier. So we looked at each phoneme class that occurred at the end of the modifier and calculated the information content for each following phoneme class. For example, the combination [2_f + 1_p] (fricative + plosive) occurs in 9,713,135 compound tokens (cf. figure 5). In total, there are 17,242,357 compound modifiers ending with a fricative. The probability of E , a plosive occurring at the start of the head given that a fricative occurs at the end of the modifier, is therefore

$$p_{plosive|fricative} = \frac{9,713,135}{17,242,357} \approx 0.563$$

and the information content is

$$I_{p(plosive|fricative)} = -\log_2(0.563) = 0.828$$

The information content expresses how surprising this event is. Another name for this measurement is therefore ‘surprisal’. If plosive was the only possible phoneme class following a fricative in our data, the value would have been 0. The real value, 0.828, is still rather low. In fact, it is the lowest surprisal value for all combinations in our data, the highest value being 7.136 for the combination [2_f + 6_v] (fricative + high vowel).⁷

After we calculated a surprisal value for each combination, we grouped the combinations according to our hypotheses and visualized the distributions of surprisal values as boxplots. We will only report results based on surprisal values calculated on the token frequencies of data (cp. figure 4 and 5) in detail, but will address results based on variations of this data basis at the end of this section.

First, we will look at the hypothesis that vowel contacts are avoided. The combinations were sorted into two groups: contacts between two vowel classes and other contacts. Figure 7 shows box plots visualizing the surprisal values for both groups. Though there is overlap, we see a clear distinction between the two groups: Most vowel class contacts have higher surprisal. Using a permutation test⁸, we can determine that the difference between the average surprisal values of the two groups is significant with $p=0.01$. This indicates that contacts between vowel classes are indeed less expected.

⁷ The full table of surprisal values on the basis of tokens can be found in the appendix, section 3.2.

⁸ For examples of the use of permutation tests for determining statistical significance in corpus data cf. Koplenig 2019.

Figure 7: Boxplot of entropy values (token based) of contacts between vowel classes vs. other contacts

Next, we will test the hypothesis that contacts between the same phoneme classes (such as plosive + plosive) are avoided. The boxplots in figure 8 show the surprisal values for contacts within the same phoneme class versus other contacts. Though we see a somewhat higher surprisal for the contacts within the same phoneme class, there is a big overlap between the boxplots and the permutation test is not significant. The fact that phonemes belong to the same phoneme class does not seem to have an effect in compounding. It should be noted that we only tested for contacts of the same phoneme *class*, not contacts of the same phonemes. The latter might have a stronger impact.

Figure 8: Boxplot of surprisal values (token based), of contacts of the same phoneme class vs. other contacts

Lastly, we will look at the sonority hypothesis derived from the syllable contact law. For this, we created three groups:

- ‘less’: The following phoneme class is less sonorous than the preceding class (a ‘good’ combination according to the hypothesis)
- ‘more’: The following phoneme class is more sonorous than the preceding class (a ‘bad’ combination according to the hypothesis)
- ‘same’: The sonority of both phoneme classes is the same, i.e. phonemes of the same class come into contact. (This is the same group that was also plotted in figure 7.)

Figure 9 shows the boxplots that visualize the surprisal values of each group. It seems that there is a tendency for ‘good’ combinations, where the second element is less sonorous than the first, to have lower surprisal values.⁹ The permutation test reveals that there is indeed a significant ($p \leq 0.01$) difference of average surprisal between the ‘less’ and ‘more’ groups, but no significant difference when the ‘same’ group is compared to either of the other groups.

For a closer look, figure 10 splits the data into 15 groups according to the difference in sonority between the last phoneme of the modifier and the first phoneme of the head. As shown in table 1, each phoneme class has a number between 1 and 7, with 1 being least sonorous. By subtracting the number of the second phoneme class from the first, we arrive at the numbers on the x-axis of figure 10, e.g. a contact between 2_f and 8_v (fricative + low vowel) would have the value -6. So in this figure, the negative numbers are ‘worse’ contacts than the positive numbers as they indicate that the second element is more sonorous than the first. The boxplots show a general tendency towards lower surprisal as the differences become positive, but the trend is not continuous.

⁹ The outlier in the boxplot for the ‘more’ group is the combination [1_p + 2_f] (plosive + fricative) which has a low surprisal value (1.38), despite being a ‘bad’ contact. Of course, plosives being the least sonorous phoneme group, a plosive can never have a contact with a less sonorous phoneme and the difference in sonority to fricatives is the smallest. The surprisal value for plosive + fricative is almost the same as the value for contacts between two plosives (1.42), while contacts with any other phoneme group have markedly higher surprisal values.

Figure 9: Boxplot of surprisal values (token based), grouped by sonority contacts

Figure 10: Boxplot of surprisal values (token based), grouped by difference in sonority

As mentioned at the beginning of the section, the plots shown here are based on the token counts in our data. We recalculated the same plots omitting the 100 most frequent compounds to control for the effect of very frequent compounds (cf. figure 6). Though the boxplots look slightly different, the permutation tests gave the same results. We also calculated the plots based on type counts (cf. figures 2 and 3). Again, the permutation tests were significant for the same group contrasts.

In section 2 we reported that linking elements were counted as part of the modifier. This implies that in cases where a linking element is present, the last phoneme of this linking element was used in our study. As linking elements are a special (though common) case in compounding, we repeated our calculations excluding all compounds where linking elements were detected. Still, we could confirm the same significant differences on the basis of tokens, tokens without the 100 most frequent compounds and on basis of types.

To sum up, the following results proved stable for different configurations:

- Contacts between vowel classes have significantly higher surprisal values.
- Contacts that are ‘bad’ according to the syllable contact law have significantly higher surprisal values than those that are regarded as ‘good’.
- There were no significant results for the other tests.

4 Appendix

4.1 Rules for assigning phoneme classes

The following rules were applied to assign a phoneme class to the orthographical form of the last element of the modifier and the first element of the head word. The strategy was the same in both tasks: We looked at the end of the word (for modifiers) and at the beginning of the word (for heads) and checked longer letter combinations first. Each table lists the rules in the order in which they were applied to the orthographical surface. If a rule matched, execution was stopped and the corresponding phoneme class label was assigned.

Note that some rules in these tables are quite idiosyncratic for our dataset as we had to account for some foreign, especially English and French spellings and decided to include explicit rules for special cases to deal with ambiguity.

Rules for the phoneme class of the last phoneme of the compound modifier

execution order	letter combinations	label	class name
1	["aille", "view"]	6_v	high vowel
2	["sch", "löw"]	2_f	fricative
3	["ieh"]	6_v	high vowel
4	["th", "qu", "ig"]	1_p	plosive
5	["ch", "sh", "ph", "pf"]	2_f	fricative
6	["ng"]	3_n	nasal
7	["rh"]	5_l	liquid (r)
8	["ie", "ih", "uh", "ou", "üh", "ei", "ai", "eu", "äu", "au", "ew"]	6_v	high vowel
9	["eh", "oh", "äh", "öh", "ow", "aw"]	7_v	mid vowel
10	["ah"]	8_v	low vowel
11	["t", "d", "g", "k", "b", "c", "p"]	1_p	plosive
12	["ß", "z", "s", "f", "v", "h", "x"]	2_f	fricative
13	["n", "m"]	3_n	nasal
14	["l"]	4_l	liquid (l)
15	["r"]	5_l	liquid (r)
16	["i", "u", "y", "ü", "j", "q ¹⁰¹ "]	6_v	high vowel
17	["e", "o", "ä", "ö", "é"]	7_v	mid vowel
18	["a", "à"]	8_v	low vowel

Rules for the phoneme class of the first phoneme of the compound head

execution order	letter combinations	label	class name
1	["sch"]	2_f	fricative
2	["ch", "sh", "ph"]	2_f	fricative
3	["ei"]	8_v	high vowel
4	["t", "d", "g", "k", "b", "x", "p", "c", "q", "z"]	1_p	plosive
5	["s", "f", "v", "w", "h"]	2_f	fricative
6	["m", "n"]	3_n	nasal
7	["l"]	4_l	liquid (l)

10 “q” triggers an annotation as 6_v (high vowel) because in our data set the only modifier that ended in the letter “q” was “IQ”. As an abbreviation this is pronounced with an “u” sound at the end.

8	["r"]	5_l	liquid (r)
9	["i", "u", "ü", "j", "y"]	6_v	high vowel
10	["e", "o", "ä", "ö"]	7_v	mid vowel
11	["a"]	8_v	low vowel

4.2 Table of surprisal values, based on compound tokens

Additional tables for other data configurations are available at the OSF repository.

Modifier (last phoneme)	Head (first phoneme)	Frequency of combination	Total frequency of modifier class	p(head class modifier class)	surprisal	same class contact	vowel class contact	sonority	sonority difference
1_p	1_p	9782346	26229355	0,372954	1,42293	yes	no	same	0
1_p	2_f	10066856	26229355	0,383801	1,381569	no	no	more	-1
1_p	3_n	2236945	26229355	0,085284	3,551581	no	no	more	-2
1_p	4_l	529642	26229355	0,020193	5,630021	no	no	more	-3
1_p	5_l	1230246	26229355	0,046903	4,414164	no	no	more	-4
1_p	6_v	334875	26229355	0,012767	6,291416	no	no	more	-5
1_p	7_v	696491	26229355	0,026554	5,234934	no	no	more	-6
1_p	8_v	1351954	26229355	0,051544	4,278064	no	no	more	-7
2_f	1_p	9713135	17242357	0,56333	0,827948	no	no	less	1
2_f	2_f	3886129	17242357	0,225383	2,149551	yes	no	same	0
2_f	3_n	1657100	17242357	0,096106	3,379224	no	no	more	-1
2_f	4_l	430253	17242357	0,024953	5,324628	no	no	more	-2
2_f	5_l	195860	17242357	0,011359	6,45999	no	no	more	-3
2_f	6_v	122602	17242357	0,007111	7,135831	no	no	more	-4
2_f	7_v	212057	17242357	0,012299	6,345361	no	no	more	-5
2_f	8_v	1025221	17242357	0,059459	4,07195	no	no	more	-6
3_n	1_p	8074539	16724684	0,482792	1,050527	no	no	less	2
3_n	2_f	4626159	16724684	0,276607	1,854092	no	no	less	1
3_n	3_n	674675	16724684	0,04034	4,631642	yes	no	same	0
3_n	4_l	463551	16724684	0,027717	5,173107	no	no	more	-1
3_n	5_l	373353	16724684	0,022323	5,485295	no	no	more	-2
3_n	6_v	176727	16724684	0,010567	6,564313	no	no	more	-3
3_n	7_v	1444712	16724684	0,086382	3,533125	no	no	more	-4
3_n	8_v	890968	16724684	0,053273	4,230462	no	no	more	-5
4_l	1_p	3251965	7325810	0,443905	1,171677	no	no	less	3
4_l	2_f	2355677	7325810	0,321559	1,636847	no	no	less	2
4_l	3_n	516733	7325810	0,070536	3,825497	no	no	less	1
4_l	4_l	181935	7325810	0,024835	5,331493	yes	no	same	0
4_l	5_l	211360	7325810	0,028851	5,115214	no	no	more	-1
4_l	6_v	290147	7325810	0,039606	4,658132	no	no	more	-2
4_l	7_v	164437	7325810	0,022446	5,477381	no	no	more	-3
4_l	8_v	353556	7325810	0,048262	4,372978	no	no	more	-4
5_l	1_p	5547747	13783101	0,402504	1,312927	no	no	less	4
5_l	2_f	4131515	13783101	0,299752	1,738158	no	no	less	3

5_l	3_n	2476063	13783101	0,179645	2,476781	no	no	less	2
5_l	4_l	486991	13783101	0,035332	4,822862	no	no	less	1
5_l	5_l	300124	13783101	0,021775	5,521198	yes	no	same	0
5_l	6_v	168566	13783101	0,01223	6,353443	no	no	more	-1
5_l	7_v	203811	13783101	0,014787	6,079525	no	no	more	-2
5_l	8_v	468284	13783101	0,033975	4,879373	no	no	more	-3
6_v	1_p	1159659	2641025	0,439094	1,187397	no	no	less	5
6_v	2_f	880392	2641025	0,333352	1,58488	no	no	less	4
6_v	3_n	188100	2641025	0,071222	3,811526	no	no	less	3
6_v	4_l	169247	2641025	0,064084	3,963896	no	no	less	2
6_v	5_l	69348	2641025	0,026258	5,2511	no	no	less	1
6_v	6_v	30441	2641025	0,011526	6,438938	yes	yes	same	0
6_v	7_v	31913	2641025	0,012084	6,37081	no	yes	more	-1
6_v	8_v	111925	2641025	0,042379	4,560494	no	yes	more	-2
7_v	1_p	1724384	4290094	0,401946	1,314928	no	no	less	6
7_v	2_f	1399232	4290094	0,326154	1,616374	no	no	less	5
7_v	3_n	640368	4290094	0,149267	2,744036	no	no	less	4
7_v	4_l	148193	4290094	0,034543	4,85546	no	no	less	3
7_v	5_l	119316	4290094	0,027812	5,16815	no	no	less	2
7_v	6_v	61574	4290094	0,014353	6,122544	no	yes	less	1
7_v	7_v	43610	4290094	0,010165	6,620206	yes	yes	same	0
7_v	8_v	153417	4290094	0,035761	4,805479	no	yes	more	-1
8_v	1_p	491683	1028146	0,478223	1,064245	no	no	less	7
8_v	2_f	273897	1028146	0,266399	1,90834	no	no	less	6
8_v	3_n	137226	1028146	0,133469	2,905419	no	no	less	5
8_v	4_l	32282	1028146	0,031398	4,993171	no	no	less	4
8_v	5_l	39380	1028146	0,038302	4,706438	no	no	less	3
8_v	6_v	15351	1028146	0,014931	6,065569	no	yes	less	2
8_v	7_v	12613	1028146	0,012268	6,34899	no	yes	less	1
8_v	8_v	25714	1028146	0,02501	5,321347	yes	yes	same	0

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